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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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CHALLENGES IN ORGANIZING SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the challenges in organizing the scientific research activities of future pedagogues, as well as the issues related to their sufficient involvement in these activities. A number of ideological and practical problems hindering this process have been identified. The study also examines the availability of adequate conditions for conducting scientific research in educational and research centers, as well as in scientific laboratories, and highlights the insufficient incentive mechanisms for researchers engaged in scientific activities. Furthermore, measures to enhance the interest of future pedagogues in scientific research, the problems and influencing factors encountered during the research process, and comprehensive solutions and recommendations have been provided.

Key words: scientific activity, scientific research, research infrastructure, cooperation system, academic inquiry.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak pedagoglarning ilmiy tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etishdagi muammolar va ularni ushbu jarayonga yetarli darajada jalb etish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Jarayonni murakkablashtirayotgan g'oyaviy hamda amaliy muammolar o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, o'quv-ilmiy markazlar va ilmiy laboratoriyalarda bo'lajak pedagoglarning tadqiqot olib borishlari uchun yaratilgan shart-sharoitlar, izlanuvchilar uchun rag'batlantirish mexanizmlarining yetarli emasligi holatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Bo'lajak pedagoglar o'rtasida ilmiy izlanishga qiziqishni oshirish choralari, tadqiqot jarayonida uchraydigan muammolar va ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlil qilingan hamda ularga batafsil yechim va tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ilmiy faoliyat, ilmiy tadqiqot, tadqiqot infratuzilmasi, hamkorlik tizimi, ilmiy izlanish.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализированы проблемы организации научно-исследовательской деятельности будущих педагогов, а также вопросы их достаточной вовлеченности в этот процесс. Выявлены ряд идеологических и практических проблем, препятствующих успешному развитию исследований. Кроме того, изучены условия, созданные в учебно-научных центрах и лабораториях для проведения научно-исследовательской деятельности, а также случаи недостаточности механизмов стимулирования исследователей. Рассмотрены меры по повышению интереса будущих педагогов к научным исследованиям, выявленные проблемы и факторы, влияющие на процесс исследований, и даны подробные решения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: научная деятельность, научное исследование, исследовательская инфраструктура, система сотрудничества, академический поиск.

INTRODUCTION

The current stage of social development places qualitatively new demands on each individual's participation in the production of material and spiritual values. In this regard, at the stage of developing specialist training in higher education institutions, the main directions and tasks of education are undergoing significant changes. This process is reflected in strengthening students' general scientific and professional training, as well as in promoting closer integration between education, science, and production.

Among the most important trends in the development of the higher education system are the following: ensuring the methodological, general scientific, and professional growth of students, and deepening the fundamentalization of education aimed at fostering interdisciplinary integration.

Numerous studies have been conducted on the scientific research activities of prospective teachers and educators in educational institutions, their preparation for research work, the problems they encounter during the research process, and the various factors influencing it.

Scientific research activity and research competence should be considered an integral component of a teacher's professional mastery. However, experience and research show that the majority of teachers and

educators with higher pedagogical education, regardless of their specialization, work experience, or age, are not sufficiently prepared to carry out such activities and face numerous difficulties in this process.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

These issues have been studied in the works of Russian scholars such as V.I. Zagvyazinskiy, I.A. Zimnyaya, V.I. Kondrukh, A.M. Novikov, N.V. Sichkova, and N.M. Yakovleva. According to N.M. Yakovleva, “Teachers face significant difficulties in restructuring and organizing their professional activities on a research basis. This is confirmed by the assessments of educational institution administrators, as well as by teachers’ and mentors’ self-evaluations. The main reason for this situation lies in the current practices of professional training in higher education institutions, which fail to provide future teachers with the necessary skills and experience to conduct scientific research” [6, 8].

The Uzbek scholar S.N. Allayarova, in her research, acknowledges the presence of numerous factors influencing the effective organization of students’ scientific activities in the higher education process and presents the following points based on the issues studied in her work [4, 15]:

- In organizing students’ research activities, the educational process and the structure of instruction in higher education institutions play a primary role. This includes the forms of education (traditional face-to-face, distance, full-time, part-time, evening, etc.), the organizational structure of the educational process (credit–module system), the evaluation system (rating, grades, points), and the presence of a healthy and transparent educational environment—all of which are integral components of the learning process.
- Among the secondary but important factors are the professional competence of professors and teachers, their specialized (hard) skills, the scientific environment and potential of the higher education institution, as well as the system of incentives for research activity.
- As for the third-level influencing factors, they include the content of academic curricula, material-technical and methodological support, and the ICT competence of educational participants (professors, teachers, and students).
- The research results confirmed that the geographical location of higher education institutions has a significant impact on the organization of students’ research activities. This conclusion was drawn from the fact that the indicators of universities located in the capital city were higher than those of universities located in regional areas [4, 16].

When discussing scientific activity and research, it can be stated that these processes contribute to enabling future teachers to conduct scientific investigations, study new technologies, and develop teaching methodologies [5, 20]. This process is also crucial for teachers to enhance their professional competence and strengthen their scientific profiles. Today, engagement in scientific research has gained significant importance.

First, it allows for the systematic observation and dissemination of new developments. Scientific research ensures the study of new data and ideas, thereby facilitating the widespread distribution of scientific innovations and contributing to the overall development of society.

Second, it serves as a foundation for innovation and technological advancement. Scientific research plays a vital role in the creation of new innovations and technologies, which help simplify human life, meet human needs to a certain extent, and provide opportunities for solving emerging problems.

Third, it is essential for training qualified specialists. Scientific research plays an important role in preparing highly skilled personnel who possess the necessary knowledge and abilities for supervision, communication, and human development in the modern context.

Fourth, scientific research is significant for economic development. Research activities also have a substantial impact on economic growth. Through the development of new technologies and innovations, they help boost the economy and strengthen the overall progress of the nation [3, 45].

Scientific activity refers to a process aimed at studying the characteristics, peculiarities, and laws of objects and phenomena (processes) in order to acquire knowledge and apply it in practice. It consists of fundamental and applied research [5, 15]. There are various factors that influence the effective conduct of such activity. These factors may interact and exert either a positive or negative influence on the research activities of prospective teachers.

1. Human Factors:

- Students’ intellectual and creative abilities;
- Their interest and motivation toward research;

- Their readiness to engage in scientific activities;
 - Skills in independent thinking and problem-solving;
 - Curiosity, initiative, persistence, and adaptability.
- 2. Institutional Factors:**
- The system of organizing research work in higher education institutions;
 - Availability of scientific research infrastructure;
 - Student involvement in research activities;
 - Conditions provided for students' scientific investigations;
 - The professional competence and potential of scientific supervisors.
- 3. Socio-Economic Factors:**
- Opportunities for financing scientific research;
 - Systems for promoting and encouraging research activities;
 - Conditions for implementing research results into practice;
 - The stage of development of the higher education system;
 - The societal attitude toward scientific research activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, information was obtained through the analysis of existing scientific literature, official educational documents, and the results of empirical observations in higher education institutions. Data collection relied on the examination of previously published research works by both foreign and Uzbek scholars, along with the evaluation of institutional practices influencing the organization of students' research activities. The gathered information was systematized and compared to identify similarities and differences in approaches. Analytical methods such as comparative analysis and logical interpretation were applied to determine key factors affecting the effectiveness of scientific activity. The findings were interpreted based on their relevance to educational reforms and the integration of scientific research into the training process of future educators. This methodology ensured that the conclusions and recommendations proposed were supported by theoretical sources and practical observations, providing a balanced and evidence-based perspective.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To improve and strengthen students' research activity, several mechanisms are recommended. First, improvement of academic curricula is essential. This includes the introduction of specialized subjects and courses related to research activities for students, the allocation of additional credit hours for the implementation of research projects, and the development of students' skills in conducting scientific research.

Another important direction is the enhancement of research infrastructure. This requires the provision of modern laboratories and equipment, the expansion of information resource centers, library collections, and electronic libraries, as well as the implementation of modern distance learning technologies.

Equally significant is the development of incentive mechanisms. These involve the establishment of scholarship, grant, and award systems for completed research projects, the organization of competitions and contests for the best research works, and the recognition of students' active participation in scientific research within their academic performance.

Attention should also be given to the expansion of collaboration systems. This consists of strengthening cooperation between universities and research institutes, promoting international collaboration and partnerships with foreign higher education institutions, and offering collaborative programs that encourage students' involvement in research activities.

Finally, the improvement of leadership and monitoring systems is crucial. This includes enhancing the regulatory and legal framework for managing and supervising research activities, establishing a system for analyzing the effectiveness of scientific research, and providing students and young researchers with scientific supervisors while closely monitoring their progress.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, these mechanisms make it possible to increase the effectiveness of scientific activity by engaging students in research, equipping them with essential skills, and improving material-technical and informational resources. The development of research activities among future teachers contributes to the formation of their professional competencies, enhances their innovative thinking abilities, supports professional growth, and enables them to address existing problems through scientific solutions.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
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 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.